

Experimental Investigation of Concrete Beam with and without FRP Wrapping

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Abstract— This study has been undertaken to investigate about the flexural as well as the tensional strength of the beam and the cylinder without using any FRP and with using FRP of different Carbon Sheet of various GSM and glass fibres to find whether FRP is beneficial for retrofitting of models of Structures. Fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) has the advantages of high strength, light weight, convenient construction, and corrosion resistance. In recent years, it has been widely used in civil engineering, especially the repair and strengthening of old structures.

Index Terms— Fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP), Grams Per Meter (GSM)

I. INTRODUCTION

The technology of FRP strengthening and repair of reinforced concrete structures is to paste the carbon fiber cloth on the surface of the concrete with a supporting adhesive resin to play a role in structural strengthening and seismic strengthening. At present, there are mainly two common process methods used for FRP to strengthen the old structure. One is the wet bonding method, that is, the FRP cloth is not moistened and pasted with resin on site. The other is to prefabricate FRP materials into various profiles, such as pultruded sheets for perimeter and shells made of filaments for column strengthening. Among them, the wet bonding method has wide applicability in on-site construction. Applicable to various types of structures (buildings, structures, bridges, tunnels, chimneys, etc.) various structural shapes (rectangular, circular, curved, etc.), various structural parts (beams, plates, columns, nodes, arches, shells, piers, etc.) are currently the most widely used. When FRP material is used for shear reinforcement, the shear capacity of the beam is also significantly improved. This shows that after the occurrence of oblique concrete cracks, FRP material can be used as the web tie rod of the truss model to improve the stress state in the reinforced concrete beam and increase the shear capacity. On the other hand, it plays a role of shear reinforcement by limiting the development of diagonal cracks.

Carbon fibres are created when polyacrylonitrile fibres (PAN), Pitch resins, or Rayon are carbonized (through oxidation and thermal pyrolysis) at high temperatures. Through further processes of graphitizing or stretching, the fibres strength or elasticity can be enhanced respectively. Carbon fibres are manufactured in

diameters analogous to glass fibres with diameters ranging from 4 to 17 μm . These fibres wound into larger threads for transportation and further production processes. Glass fibers are typically produced by mixing silica sand, limestone, folic acid, and other minor ingredients, which are then heated until they melt at approximately 1260°C. The molten glass is drawn through fine holes in a platinum plate, cooled, gathered, and wound. These fibers, woven into various forms, offer high electrical insulating properties, low susceptibility to moisture, and significant mechanical properties. Despite being impact-resistant, glass fibers are heavier compared to carbon or aramid.

Types of Fibre

Fig. 1 Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer

Fig. 1 Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer

Application of FRP

- Fibre-reinforced plastics are best suited for any design program that demands weight savings, precision engineering, definite tolerances, and the simplification of parts in both production and operation.
- The fibers provide strength and stiffness to the material, while the polymer matrix holds the fibers together and transfers loads between them.
- FRP composites have a wide range of applications across various industries due to their unique combination of properties, including high strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, and design flexibility.
- A moulded polymer product is cheaper, faster, and easier to manufacture than a cast aluminium or steel product, and maintains similar and sometimes better tolerances and material strengths.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

- 1) **Solauddin Bin Azuwa, Fadzil Beam Mat Yaha, etal (May 2024)** **Title : Experimental investigation and finite element analysis of reinforced concrete beams strengthened by fibre reinforced polymer composite materials.**
 - FRP reinforcement enhances the rigidity, load capacity, and overall performance of reinforced concrete beams.
 - GFRP is commonly used due to its cost-effectiveness compared to other FRP materials.
 - Large gaps in unstrengthened beams lead to abnormal flexural fractures, reduced strength, stiffness, and increased deflection compared to FRP-reinforced beams.
- 2) **Prof. Akshay.V.Sawdekar, Sakshi.R. Gaikwad,etal. (2023)** **Title : A Review Paper on Experimental Study on Retrofitting of Beam With CFRP**
 - The use of CFRP materials is an effective technique for strengthening concrete structural reinforced members.
 - Strengthening RC beams with CFRP fabric increases load-carrying capacity and stiffness.
 - Wrapping the two lateral sides and soffit improves performance and serviceability.
 - Increased application of CFRP fabrics enhances stiffness and rigidity, preventing sudden crushing or destruction.
 - Applying CFRP fabrics considering area, rigidity, and stiffness increases beam strength and provides additional load-carrying capacity.
- 3) **Ahmed.S.Eisa, Mustafa.H.Ahmed, etal. (2023)** **Title : Experimental investigation on the behaviour of fly-ash based geopolymer reinforced concrete beams strengthened with CFRP.** **Journal- Heliyon Cell Press e17674**
 - The mid-span deflection of flexural GPC beams strengthened with different configurations of CFRP sheets (single flat layer, u-shape single layer, and double flat layer) decreased by 23%, 11%, and 16%, respectively, resulting in an average deflection decrease of about 16%
- 4) **Muhammad Fahim, Muhammad Saeed, etal. (2022)** **Title : Flexure Behaviour of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers Retrofitted RC Beams (2022)** **Advances in Science and Technology Research Journal ISSN 2299-862**
 - CFRP strips (Sika Carbo-Dur S812) and wraps (Sika-Wrap 230C) were used in two different patterns to evaluate their effect on the flexural behaviour of RC beams.
 - Two beams were first tested until their ultimate capacity, retrofitted with the application of CFRP and re-tested again, and two beams were retrofitted before the application of any load.
 - even a simple anchorage scheme can increase the effectiveness of CFRP retrofitting by delaying the spread of micro-cracking and de-bonding.
- 5) **Mina Dawood, Prakash Poudel, etal (sept-2022)** **Title : Flexural behaviour of full-scale, carbon-fibre-reinforced polymer prestressed concrete beams** **PCI Journal**
 - A total of eight prestressed concrete beams (three with prestressing CFRP cables, four with prestressing CFRP bars, and one with prestressing steel) were fabricated and tested under two flexural loading conditions: monotonic flexure and flexural fatigue.
 - CFRP prestressed concrete beams demonstrated a higher strength (1.5 times the capacity for the same number of prestressing elements) and similar or lower deformability compared with steel prestressed concrete beams.
 - The wide distribution of cracks and large deformation at failure for CFRP prestressed concrete beams indicates that CFRP prestressed concrete beams provide enough warning before failure.

- 6) **Chetan Yalburgimath, Akshar Rathod, etal (2022)**
Title : Retrofitting of Reinforced Concrete Beam Using Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) Fabric (2022)
- The use of CFRP materials is an effective technique for strengthening concrete structural reinforced members.
 - Strengthening RC beams with CFRP fabric increases load-carrying capacity and stiffness.
 - Wrapping the two lateral sides and soffit improves performance and serviceability.
 - Increased application of CFRP fabrics enhances stiffness and rigidity, preventing sudden crushing or destruction.
 - Applying CFRP fabrics considering area, rigidity, and stiffness increases beam strength and provides additional load-carrying capacity.
- 7) **Ana De Digo, Sonia Martinez. (May 2022)**
Title : Experimental investigation on the compressive behaviour of FRP-confined rectangular concrete columns
- The efficiency of FRP confinement decreases as the aspect ratio of the rectangular section increases. In the experimental study, specimens with three CFRP plies and a concrete strength (f_{co}) of 34.4 MPa achieved an average strength enhancement ratio (f_{cc}/f_{co}) of 2.19 when $h/b=1$ and 1.41 when $h/b=1.5$. For specimens with three CFRP plies and $f_{co}=29.8$ MPa, the strength enhancement ratio was only 1.16 when $h/b=2$. Additionally, an improvement in compressive strength was observed with an increase in the corner radius.
 - Despite the decrease in efficiency with increasing aspect ratio, significant improvements in concrete properties, especially for low-strength concrete, can be achieved by increasing the amount of FRP reinforcement in rectangular sections with aspect ratios of 1.5 and 2. Strength enhancement ratios (f_{cc}/f_{co}) of up to 1.81 and 1.36 were obtained in the study for aspect ratios of 1.5 and 2, respectively.
- 8) **Maheid Vahid Pour, Ali Kehy Roddin, etal. (2022)**
Title :Experimental Investigation on Flexural Capacity of Reinforced Concrete Beams Strengthened with 3D-Fiberglass, CFRP and GFRP
:ISSN 1976-0485 / eISSN 2234-1315
- The effectiveness of 3D-fiberglass with resin exceeded that of FRP systems in terms of flexural capacity. The R3DTR and RGFRP specimens showed the highest and lowest flexural capacity growth, with 19% and 8.4%, respectively. Additionally, the U-wrap of 3D-fiberglass significantly increased the ultimate load (up to 30% compared to the REF specimen), demonstrating the effectiveness of this strengthening approach
 - Strengthening the specimens by adding sheets to the concrete surface led to reduced ductility. The reduction in ductility was lower in the specimens with 3D-fiberglass compared to those strengthened with FRP. Furthermore, the U-wrap of 3D-fiberglass reduced ductility (up to 27%) in comparison to specimens strengthened with 3D-fiberglass without any wrapping.
- 9) **Akshay Shivankar, K.R.Dabhekar, etal (2021)**
Title :Behaviour of Simply Supported Concrete Beam Using CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer)
 IOP Publishing 1197 (2021) 012033
- Study the behaviour of beam with the use of CFRP composite by experimentally and by ANSYS and compare both the results and compare load carrying capacity
 - For experimentally we cast Nine no's of beam of size $100 \times 100 \times 400$ mm, of M30 grade of concrete and curing for 7 days and after 7 days curing , conduct
- 10) **Behavior of Simply Supported Concrete Beam using CFRP (2021)**
- CFRP wrapping can enhance resistance of concrete beam and reduce their deflection and decrease the damage percentage.
 - Beams strengthened with CFRP exhibit increased flexural strength, enhanced flexural stiffness and composite action until failure.
- 11) **Experimental Investigation of Reinforced Concrete Beam with Openings Strengthened Using FRP Sheets under Cyclic Load (8 July 2020)**
- Experiments and numerical simulations showed that openings in the shear or flexural zone significantly affect beam capacity, stiffness degradation, energy absorption, and failure mode.
 - FRP strengthening effectively restored the original beam capacity.
 - The FRP sheet improved the total strength by 66.69% and 74.84% for openings in the shear and flexural zones, respectively.
- 12) **Hemanth Kumar, Ruben Nerella, etal. (June,2019)**
Title :Art-of-review on CFRP Wrapping to Strengthen Compressive and Flexural Behavior of Concrete.
International Information and Engineering Technology Association Vol. 29
- Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) materials are recognized as vital constituents to solve stability issues of the modern concrete structures. The purpose of present constructive studies of various techniques for FRP retrofit concrete structures because, the FRP material has improves the structural performance in terms of stability, stiffness, strength and durability such that the Fibre-Reinforced Polymers wrapping is one of the techniques to regain the strength of a concrete structures.
 - various wrapping techniques of FRP sheets for external strengthening of RC structures such as reinforced circular columns, square beams, columns and column-beam joints.
 - different wrappings techniques are used to regain the strength and also enhanced the durability of the structure

13) Johannes Tarigal, Andrew Pakpahan, etal. (2019)

Title :Analysis and experimental usage of CFRP wrap type on flexural strength of concrete beam

MATEC Web of Conferences 258, 03001 (2019)

- Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) Wrap Type as the external reinforcement. The beam's dimension was 15 x 25 cm with a length of 320 cm. Based on the analysis results, the beam using CFRP Wrap type can increase the load 3.12 % times.
- he experimental results show that the beam with the CFRP type Wrap increases the load by 2.5 times.
- beams strengthened with CFRP Wrap type can inhibit initial cracks and hold the tensile and flexural strength greater than un-strengthened beams.
- by adding external strengthening whether CFRP Plate and Wrap can increase beam ability on carrying flexure much more better than its normal condition (without strengthening).

14) Ramgopal.L, M. Abhinav (March 2019)

Title :Study On The Behaviour Of Reinforced Concrete Beams Using CFRP Laminates In Flexural Zone

International Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences (IJEAS) ISSN: 2394-3661, Volume-6, Issue-3

- a study on the behaviour of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) laminates as a flexural repair system for Reinforced Concrete (RC) beams
- to investigate the flexural behaviour of RC beams strengthened by carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates.
- he experimental program includes testing of 3 simply supported reinforced concrete beams of which 2 beams are strengthened with CFRP laminates, the remaining 1 beam will be fully solid without CFRP laminates and considered as control beam
- The deflection, cracking pattern and ultimate load carrying capacity for RC beams bonded with CFRP laminates is investigated.
- All the beams strengthened with CFRP laminates showed improvement in the structural performance.
- CFRP laminates proved to be effective material for repair and strengthening of beam. Further investigation can be done with even more wrapping schemes for better improvement in structural performance of beam.

15) Title :Analysis and Experimental usage of CFRP Wrap type on flexural strength of Concrete Beam (2019)

- Combining CFRP and reinforcement achieved better results than reinforcement alone.
- The analysis obtained on steel plate there is an increase in load of 2.61 times, while on CFRP plate is 2.96 times, on GFRP is 2.67, and on CFRP Wrap is 3.12 times.

16) Praveen Kumar, Sekar.B, etal. (2018)

Title :Experimental Investigation on Strengthening of RCC beams by Wrapping Glass Fiber Reinforced polymer Sheet

International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) Volume: 05 Issue: 06

e-ISSN: 2395-0056 p-ISSN: 2395-0072

- The study focused on the behavior of rectangular concrete beams with GFRP wrap and compared their strength and behavior to conventional concrete beams.
- The research project concluded that GFRP wrapping at the tension side provides better strength compared to wrapping at two parallel sides.
- However, the strength is lower than when GFRP is wrapped at three sides.
- Wrapping GFRP at three sides results in higher strength.
- Despite the increased strength, the cost of using GFRP composites in construction is a concern as it raises the overall construction cost.

17) M.Neez Shaik, Patrick R Martini, etal (2018)

Eccentrically Loaded FRP Confined Concrete with Different Wrapping Schemes

Journal of Composites for Construction, 22 (6), 04018056-1-04018056-15.

- This study presents the results of an experimental program on the comparative performance of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) confined concrete specimens with different wrapping schemes.
- The test results indicate that fully wrapped specimens outperformed other groups of specimens under both concentric and eccentric axial loads, which were followed by nonuniformly and partially wrapped specimens

18) Huisu Chen, Fangyalzhang, etal. (2017)

Title :Experimental study of the mechanical behavior of FRP-reinforced concrete canvas panels.

- The tensile strength of CC with AFRP reinforcement reaches 8.74 MPa for the warp direction and 8.76 MPa for the weft direction, about 6 and 9 times respectively higher than that of CC alone (1.36 MPa for the warp direction and 0.99 MPa for the weft direction under max minimum load).
- The flexural strength of CC with AFRP reinforcement is 50.86 MPa for the warp direction and 42.86 MPa for the weft direction, about 20 times greater than that of CC alone (2.4 MPa for the warp direction and 2.15 MPa for the weft direction).
- The results also show that the flexural strength of CC with AFRP reinforcement along the warp direction is nearly 16% higher than that measured along the weft direction.

Overview of Literature

Fiber reinforced polymer wrapping involves, The substrate can be prepared by applying resin with a trowel or roller, or by sealing it with epoxy resin. The fabric can be applied dry or wet. Flexure or shear-critical beams were provided with CFRP longitudinal sheets like single layer, double layers etc or U-wraps, respectively. Concrete beams reinforced internally with steel and externally with carbon FRP. the beam with mentioned carbon fabric than minimum 1.5 times

strength increase in the both the case flexure and shear. Moment carrying capacity of single layer beam, double layer beam, at centre and fully u shaped beam is increase by 12-18%, 15-30%, 35-50% and 60-75% respectively. Increasing the layer of FRP and the axial compressive load could also reduce the impact deformation attributable to the enhancement of the overall integrity and general stiffness.

III. AIM & OBJECTIVE

Aim:

The primary aim of this experimental investigation is to calculate the structural performance of fresh concrete beams and cylinders with and without Fiber Reinforced Polymer-FRP wrapping

Objective

- To verify the property of concrete and FRP sheets
- To conduct different test on the Material
- Mix Design calculation
- Casting and Testing of the Beams

IV EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Mix Proportions: (M30 Grade)

Mass of Cement -	290 kg/m ³
Mass of Water -	145 kg/m ³
Mass of Fine Aggregate -	696 kg/m ³
Mass of Coarse Aggregate -	1429 kg/m ³
Mass of Admixture -	Nil
Water Cement Ratio -	0.5

Experimental Program:

	No. of Beams	No. of Cylinders	Quantity Of FRP
Plain Concrete	3	3	-
200 GSM (CFRP)	3	3	3.45m
900 GSM (GFRP)	3	3	3.45m
Total	9	9	8 M FRP

V. TEST RESULTS

1. Test Data for the Beams with and without the FRP

Fig. 3 Beam without FRP wrapping

Fig. 4 Beam with Glass FRP (GFRP) wrapping

Fig. 5 Beam with Carbon FRP (CFRP) wrapping

2. Test Data for the Cylinder with and without the FRP

Fig. 6 Cylinder with Glass FRP (GFRP) wrapping

Fig. 7 Cylinder with Carbon FRP (CFRP) wrapping

Fig. 8 Interpretation of Results for Split tensile strength

Fig. 8 Interpretation of Results for Flexural strength

VI. CONCLUSION

Strength Improvement: FRP wrapping significantly enhances the compressive and tensile strength of concrete elements. The composite materials effectively distribute stress and improve loadbearing capacity. We have come to conclusion that the flexural strength of the beam increases up to 20% by using the CFRP and 15% by using the GFRP. Overall, the study underscores the effectiveness of FRP wrapping as a viable technique for improving the mechanical properties of concrete structures, making it a valuable tool in civil engineering applications

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